

1 ACCELERATED CARBONATION OF
2 CERAMIC MATERIALS. APPLICATION TO
3 BRICKS FROM ANDALUSIAN FACTORIES
4 (SPAIN)

5 *Domingo Martín*, Patricia Aparicio, Emilio Galán*

6 Dpto. Cristalografía, Mineralogía y Química Agrícola, Facultad de Química, Universidad
7 de Sevilla, C/ Profesor García González, 1, Sevilla 41012, Spain.

8

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10

11 ABSTRACT

12 This research explores the possibility of CO₂ sequestration in ceramic building materials,
13 namely bricks. The bricks used are rich in calcium and magnesium. The reaction with
14 CO₂ was carried out in sealed reactor with a 0.3 L volume in a CO₂ atmosphere at
15 pressures of 10 bars. The solid-water ratio was 4:1, and the reaction time ranged from 24
16 hours to 30 days. The results show that the carbonation was proportional to the reaction
17 time. Those results open new future possibilities using brick waste to the capture of CO₂
18 in ambient temperature and low pressure.

19 **1. Introduction**

20 The increase in average global temperatures since the mid-20th century may be ascribed
21 to the increased emission of anthropogenic greenhouse gases [1]. Generally, human
22 activities result in emissions of four long-lived **greenhouse gases (GHGs)**: CO₂, CH₄, NO
23 and halocarbons. Of these, CO₂ is the most important anthropogenic GHG, because it
24 has increased approximately 40% from the preindustrial era, as a consequence of fossil
25 fuel consumption and changes in soil use [2]. To avoid the potentially devastating
26 consequences of global warming and climate change, anthropogenic CO₂ emissions into
27 the atmosphere should be reduced considerably. However, achieving such reductions
28 through reducing energy intensity or switching to less carbon intensive fuels, with parallel
29 increases in the use of renewable energies, seems to be unrealistic. Therefore,
30 technological proposals have been put forward for reducing emissions into the
31 atmosphere by means of **carbon dioxide capture and storage (CCS)**. This strategy
32 involves the development of innovative, available and cost-effective technologies.

33 Storage of CO₂ may be carried out through a number of mechanisms, including mineral
34 carbonation, oceanic storage, underground injection for enhanced fossil fuel recovery,
35 and injection into saline aquifers **[1,3–10]**.

36 Carbon dioxide sequestration by mineral carbonation mimics naturally occurring rock
37 weathering. In this natural process, CO₂ and water play an important role in dissolving
38 unstable rock-forming minerals (i.e., K-feldspar, plagioclases, olivine, pyroxenes, and
39 others, depending on the rock composition), releasing alkali and alkaline-earths cations
40 and forming mostly phyllosilicates.

41 The mineral carbonation process as an alternative for CO₂ reduction was originally
42 proposed by Seifritz [11]. The main advantage of this process is that the formed minerals
43 are similar to end products of geologic processes and are known to be stable over
44 geological time periods (millions of years). In addition, the reaction products can be
45 environmentally accepted.

46 The capture of CO₂ follows the reaction:

48 where M is a metallic element such as calcium, magnesium or iron.

49 There are many suitable magnesium or calcium silicates such as enstatite, anorthite,
50 diopside, talc, which are potential sources for both CaO and MgO. However, not all of
51 these silicates are abundant in the Earth's surface, and direct carbonation is not easy
52 under low-pressure and low-temperature conditions. Experiments using reactors for the
53 carbonation of magnesium silicates (wollastonite and serpentine), via magnesium oxide
54 or magnesium hydroxide intermediates, have been carried out at temperatures and
55 pressures up to 600°C and 100 bars (allowing for both sub- and supercritical conditions
56 for CO₂) [12–14], or under hydrothermal conditions, in the case of anorthite [15] and
57 several Ca and Mg-rich minerals [16,17]. However, these conditions are not very cost-
58 effective.

59 According to Fauth et al. [18], Lackner et al. [19] and Zevenhoven et al. [20],
60 mineralization of CO₂ has benefits, especially at locations where the risk of leakage is
61 considered unacceptable or where underground storage sites are not available while vast
62 resources of suitable magnesium silicates exist. Wollastonite is a rare mineral, and when

63 a wollastonite deposit exists, mining is preferable because it is a very important and
64 expensive industrial mineral. Serpentine is more widely distributed, but the main
65 serpentinized massifs are located in only some countries. Diopside, anorthite and other
66 Mg/Ca pyroxenes and amphiboles are rock-forming minerals, but they do not occur as
67 mineral deposits.

68 Other sources of Mg and Ca have been explored for potential carbonation, including Mg-
69 or Ca-containing mine tailings and by-products or wastes from industry. This has included
70 investigation of the carbonation of fly-ash [21], steel making slag [22–25], asbestos-
71 mining tailings, electric arc furnace (EAF) dust, cement-kiln dust, waste concrete, and air
72 pollution control (APC) residues [9,26]. In addition, natural carbonation in the formation
73 of carbonated cement systems has been well-known for many years. Alkaline earth
74 hydroxide cements and mortars harden slowly due to their reaction with atmospheric CO₂.

75 Other well-known carbonation processes occur in ceramic building materials. These
76 ceramics are rich in Ca/Mg silicates formed at high temperature during heating, in contact
77 with atmospheric CO₂ and humidity such minerals can be carbonated [27]. Moreover, in
78 many low-quality bricks the presence of CaO is common, and carbonation is very quick.
79 Fabbri et al. [27] present a review of the presence of calcite on ceramic materials,
80 indicating that the calcite can be of primary or secondary origin. Primary calcite includes
81 the forms of calcite that are preserved without change during the ceramic firing.
82 Secondary calcite (anthropogenic calcite) includes all the forms of calcite that crystallize
83 in the ceramics after firing, irrespective of the time, the cause, and the grain size.

84 Taking into account the easy carbonation of ceramic building materials, this research
85 aims to carbonate bricks in the laboratory, in order to develop a procedure that could be
86 industrially profitable. The main carbonation mechanisms were studied in the presence
87 of water to simulate an accelerated carbonation process.

88

89 **2. Materials and Methods**

90 Three bricks from different Andalusian (South Spain) brickworks were chosen for
91 carbonation tests. The brick MPC2 was a clinker brick made in Bailen (Jaén), fired at
92 1050°C. The brick AUC1 was a perforated brick made in La Puebla de Cazalla (Sevilla),
93 heated at 900°C and the brick MSC1 was a hollow ceramic block from Jun (Granada),
94 heated at approximately 800°C. **The bricks were ground in a jaw crusher and sieved in**
95 **laboratory.**

96 The carbonation tests were carried out in a 0.3 L volume hermetic reactor from Parr
97 Instrument. The fixed conditions were 10 bars of CO₂, 4:1 solid-water ratio and room
98 temperature. The variable conditions were the reaction time (between 24 and 720 hours)
99 and the particle size (> 4 mm, 2-4 mm, and 1-2 mm) (Table 1). These particle-size
100 fractions were selected because they are the most representative results of the crushing
101 treatment.

102

103 **Table 1.** Experimental parameter values during the carbonation reaction tests.

104 After finishing the carbonation tests, treated samples were dried at 70°C for 24 hours,
105 powdered, and sieved at 100 µm for subsequent analysis.

106 The mineralogical composition of the untreated and treated samples was identified by X-
107 ray diffraction (XRD), using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with standard
108 monochromatic CuK α radiation operating at 40 kV and 30 mA. Scanning was performed
109 with a 0.015° 2 θ step size at 0.1 s per step between 3-70°. Also, Rietveld refinement was
110 realized to determine the quantitative composition of untreated bricks, in this case, the
111 scanning was performed with a 0.010° 2 θ step size at 0.5 s per step between 3-120° and
112 adding zincite as internal standard.

113 The major elemental composition expressed in oxides was performed by X-ray
114 fluorescence (XRF) with an automated Panalytical Axios model spectrometer. The
115 samples were prepared for analysis as glass discs.

116 The carbonated content of the raw and carbonated samples was determined by two
117 different analytical methods: thermal decomposition (DTA-TG) and elemental analysis.
118 DTA-TG analyses were performed in a TG Netzsch STA 409PC. Samples (approximately
119 150 mg) were heated in an aluminium oxide crucible under a nitrogen atmosphere at 10°C
120 min⁻¹ from room temperature to 1200°C. Weight loss was measured by TG in the range
121 of 450-900°C relative to the total carbonated decomposition. The elemental carbon
122 content was also measured using an elemental analyser, LECO CHNS 932, which
123 calculates the carbonated ratio.

124 Soluble Si, Ca and Mg ions of the original and treated samples were also determined.

125 The analysis was performed with simultaneous inductively-coupled plasma optical

126 spectrometry (ICP-OES) analysis using a Horiba Jobin Yvon ULTIMA 2 model instrument.
127 The samples were prepared by mixing the solid powder samples with water and stirring
128 for 24 h, afterwards isolating the liquid phase by centrifugation and filtered using a Nylon
129 0.22 µm syringe filter.

130 The specific surface area (BET) was measured with a Micromeritics Gemini 2360
131 instrument using the absorption of N₂ at liquid nitrogen temperature. Prior to measuring,
132 all the samples were degassed at 80°C for 12 h and finally outgassed to 10⁻³ Torr.

133 Macro and micro observations were obtained by stereomicroscope using a Greenough
134 Leica S8 APO equipped with a DC300 camera, and by scanning electronic microscopy
135 (SEM) using a JEOL 6460 LV microscope and FEI Teneo, both equipped with energy
136 dispersive spectrometers (Oxford Instruments INCA and EDAX, respectively). The
137 samples were prepared with Au-sputter coating for improve the imagining of the samples.
138 Topography measurements were carried out using a non-contact 3D optical profiler
139 Sensofar S-Neox.

140

141 3. Results and Discussion

142 Calcium oxide in the bricks ranges from 15-24 wt%, and magnesium oxide ranges from
143 2-4 wt% (Table 2). Such high Ca-materials seem to be appropriate for mineral
144 carbonation.

145 **Table 2.** Major oxide composition (wt%) by XRF of selected bricks.

146

147 The bricks are composed of quartz and cristobalite (SiO_2), diopside ($\text{CaMgSi}_2\text{O}_6$) and
148 minor orthoclase (KAlSi_3O_8). Other silicates were also detected, such as wollastonite
149 (CaSiO_3) in MPC2 and AUC1, anorthite ($\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$) in MPC2, and gehlenite
150 ($\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}(\text{AlSi})\text{O}_7$) in MSC1 (Table 3). Anhydrite (CaSO_4) was also identified in AUC1 and
151 MSC1; in the latter sample, mica, and traces of calcite and hematite were also found. This
152 mineralogy is consistent with the chemical analysis and the heating temperature of these
153 ceramic materials.

154 **Table 3.** Mineralogical composition (wt%) of selected bricks.

155 **Legend** [28]: Qtz: quartz; Anh: anhydrite; Wo: wollastonite; Crs: cristobalite; Or:
156 orthoclase; Ab: albite; Di: diopside; An: anorthite; Gh: gehlenite; Mca: mica; Cal: calcite;
157 Hem: hematite; Amorph: amorphous phase.

158

159 **On the other hand**, minor free Ca ions are available (100-800 mg/l) to precipitate as
160 carbonates during the reaction with carbonic acid that is produced by the combination of
161 CO_2 gas and humidity.

162 ~~The bricks were ground in a jaw crusher and sieved in laboratory, obtaining the following~~
163 ~~a particle size distribution~~ The fractions > 4 mm, 2 - 4 mm and 1 - 2 mm represent more
164 than 80% of the samples (Table 4). Therefore, those fractions were selected for
165 carbonated tests.

166 **Table 4.** Granulometric fractions of the crushed samples (wt%).

167

168 X-ray diffraction patterns of the untreated and treated samples (for different particle size
169 fractions and after 720 h reaction time) are shown in Fig. 1. For MPC2 (Fig. 1a), the most
170 obvious differences with the treatment are the presence of calcite and the depletion of
171 wollastonite and some orthoclase. Attack of wollastonite with carbonic acid allows the
172 release of calcium ions and calcite precipitation. Concerning the presence of soluble ions
173 (Fig. 2a), the amount of Ca ions decreases over the reaction time, because of calcite
174 precipitation, while Si increases as a consequence of the partial destruction of silicate.

175

176 **Figure 1.** Mineralogical evolution of MPC2 after 720 hours of reaction, with three particle
177 sizes. a) MPC2 with significant detail, b) AUC1 with significant detail, and c) MSC1.

178 **Abbreviations:** Qtz: quartz; Anh: anhydrite; Wo: wollastonite; Crs: cristobalite; Or: orthoclase; Ab: albite;
179 Di: diopside; An: anorthite; Gh: gehlenite; Mca: mica; Cal: calcite; Hem: hematite; Amorph: amorphous
180 phase.

181

182 **Figure 2.** a) Soluble Ca, Mg, and Si ions measured in untreated and treated MPC2 after
183 240 and 720 hours of reaction; b) Soluble Ca (divided by 10), Mg, and Si ions measured
184 in untreated and treated AUC1 after 240 and 720 hours of reaction; c) Soluble Ca (/10),
185 Mg (/10), and Si ions measured in untreated and treated MSC1 after 240 and 720 hours
186 of reaction.

187

188 For the sample AUC1 (Fig. 1b), besides the attack of wollastonite and some orthoclase,
189 anhydrite destruction was also observed. Therefore, wollastonite and anhydrite were the

190 main sources of calcium to form calcite. In AUC1, the behaviour of soluble ions (Fig. 2b)
191 was similar to that observed for MPC2, at least for the larger fraction studied. It is to be
192 noted that for the smaller fractions the soluble calcium content increases over the reaction
193 time, because of the significant attack of calcium silicates.

194 In case of MSC1 (Fig. 1c), the main source of calcium was anhydrite, while attack of
195 gehlenite (and mica) was negligible. Nevertheless, in this sample the presence of a
196 calcium-magnesium carbonate phase was identified. The origin of this Mg must be the
197 result of some diopside alteration, because, in spite of the fact that it was not observed
198 by XRD, the chemical analysis of soluble ions showed an increase in magnesium content
199 as a function of reaction time (Fig. 2c).

200 Therefore, the carbonation process occurs in two steps: a) silicate mineral dissolution,
201 and b) carbonate precipitation. Several studies based on mineral carbonation of
202 wollastonite [29–31] described the process in aqueous carbonation route as:

203 1. Dissolution of CO₂ in water and production of (bi-)carbonate:

205 2. Leaching of Ca from wollastonite by acidic attack:

207 3. Finally, nucleation and growth of calcium carbonate:

209 The case of anhydrite has not been so widely studied. Mayoral et al. (2013) [32] based
210 on mineral carbonation process by lime-rich coal ashes proposed that the solubility of
211 calcium sulfate increases with increasing [OH⁻]. So, the dissolution of calcium sulfate
212 produce a liberation of an extra amount of available Ca²⁺ cations, following the reaction:

214 And the carbonation process Ca(OH)₂ (portlandite) has been widely studied [22,30,33–
215 37].

216 On the other hand, Ji et al. (2017) [38] in their studies of fly ash mineralization showed a
217 partial destruction of anhydrite with CO₂, but that calcium was unreactive at ambient
218 conditions.

219 According to the C-elemental and the TG results, the carbonation produced is directly
220 related with the reaction time for MPC2 and AUC1 (Figs. 3a and b), reaching up to 2.7
221 wt% and 8.9 wt% of CO₂ capture for the biggest fraction at 720 hours for MPC2 and
222 AUC1, respectively. In contrast, for MSC1 (Fig. 3c), the amount of CO₂ captured was
223 close to the maximum reached at 24 h of reaction (increased 2.7 wt%) and remained
224 practically constant over longer reaction times (to 3.3 wt%).

225

226 **Figure 3.** Calcite content calculated by C-content (black solid line) and DTA-TG (red dot-
227 line) analysis as a function of reaction time for (a) MPC2, (b) AUC1 and (c) MSC1.

228

229 As the calcite formation in MSC1 was not highly correlated with the available C content
230 (8-10 wt%), physical adsorption must be the main capture process occurring in this
231 sample. This process could explain why the CO₂ capture is rapid (an hour) in comparison
232 with the other samples studied.

233 On the other hand, a relationship between particle size and the amount of CO₂ captured
234 was not clearly observed.

235 The partial destruction of silicates and anhydrite resulted in a new specific surface into
236 the bulk, as showed by the BET results (Fig. 4). However, the specific surface also
237 depended on the particle size, i.e., it was higher for the larger fraction and longer reaction
238 time.

239 According to the results obtained two possibilities can explain the increase of BET
240 detected: a) the partial destruction of Ca-minerals by carbonic acid; b) the calcite
241 precipitation on the surface of the sample after mineral destruction. In addition, in MSC1
242 minor CO₂ adsorption could be supposed because C determination by elemental analyser
243 was higher than that derived from the calcite (by XRD).

244 Johnson and co-workers (2014) [39], in their study about olivine carbonation said that
245 the “dramatic” increase in BET surface area (in own study, the increase goes to 1 - 20
246 m²/g in AUC1, 1 – 7 m²/g in MPC2 and 2 – 7 m²/g in MSC1) indicate that amorphous
247 silica formed by olivine destruction and for secondary carbonate precipitation on the
248 available surface.

249

250 **Figure 4.** Specific surface evolution by BET as a function of reaction time for (a) MPC2,
251 (b) AUC1 and (c) MSC1.

252

253 **Macro and micro observations, confirming the presence of precipitated calcium**
254 **carbonate.** It is to be noted that the neoformed calcite exhibits different habits. So, at least
255 three types of crystal growth were observed. One of them consisted of parallel layers of
256 aggregates of tabular microcrystals, forming a crystal stock (Fig. 6), which in a first step
257 occurs as apparently “vitreous” sheets (Fig. 5). At the edges of these aggregates, well-
258 formed prismatic crystals of calcite were observed in the all the samples (Figs. 7a, b),
259 which were at least 500 μm thick (Fig. 7c). These crystals also appeared in separate small
260 geometric aggregates or with lamellar habit (Fig. 8a) and dendritic growth (Fig. 8b). In
261 other cases, big layers of well-formed crystals of carbonates were observed, sometimes
262 filling pores (Fig. 9).

263

264 **Figure 5.** Vitreous aspect observed by a) stereomicroscope and b) SEM for AUC1 after
265 240 hours of treatment.

266

267 **Figure 6.** a) Squamous aspect of calcite observed by stereomicroscope and b)
268 aggregates of tabular habit by SEM.

269

270 **Figure 7.** Crystal growth observed by a) stereomicroscope, b) SEM, and c) 3D optical
271 profiler for MPC2 after 720 hours of treatment.

272

273 **Figure 8.** a) Aggregates of laminar habit and b) aggregates of dendritic growth.

274

275 **Figure 9.** Layer of calcite on the surface of MPC2, observed by stereomicroscope after
276 720 hours of treatment.

277

278 The carbonation efficiency (C.E., Eq. 5) has been determined from the ratio between the
279 maximum percentage of CO₂ captured for 30 days of reaction time and the average for
280 the different fractions (experimental capture, E.C.) and the theoretical maximum CO₂
281 sequestration value obtained from the stoichiometric formula (theoretical capture, T.C.,
282 Eq. 6) [40], an approach accepted by several authors [34,41].

$$283 \quad C.E. (\%) = (E.C. / T.C.) * 100 \quad (5)$$

$$284 \quad CO_2 (\%) = 0.785(\%CaO - 0.7\%SO_3) + 1.09\%MgO + 0.71\%Na_2O + 0.468\%K_2O \quad (6)$$

285 Table 5 shows that the carbonation efficiency was higher for AUC1, followed by MSC1
286 and MPC2. Nevertheless, as the Steinour's equation does not take into account the
287 contribution of sulphates to the carbonation, that in the present study were also detected
288 for AUC1 and MSC1, the carbonation efficiency was recalculated, considering all CaO
289 available, including sulphates. Now, the theoretical maximum CO₂ capture was

290 AUC1>MPC2>MSC1. These results agree reasonably with the experimental carbonation
291 data.

292

293 **Table 5.** Carbonation Efficiency (C.E.) according to Steinour's equation and corrected.

294

295 According to the XRD data, wollastonite and/or anhydrite still remain in the treated
296 material, which could contribute to an increase in the carbonation efficiency.
297 Nevertheless, several factors could prevent CO₂ diffusion into the bulk of the sample
298 particles, such as the presence of "vitreous" sheets, the filling of the pores with carbonate
299 crystals, or a decrease in the CO₂ pressure and/or moisture necessary for the acidic
300 attack.

301

302 **4. Conclusions**

303 The present study shows the possibility of using ceramic construction wastes for
304 carbonation under surface conditions in a short period of time. Specifically, in this study
305 Ca-rich bricks were successful used as a raw material for direct mineral carbonation. In
306 addition to the destruction of Ca-silicates, anhydrites, which is occasionally present, may
307 also be attacked, and the Ca may be removed for a subsequent precipitation of
308 carbonates.

309 The amount of carbonation is proportional to the time of reaction (the longer the time, the
310 higher the capture efficiency), whereas it does not seem to significantly depend on the
311 particle size in the conditions studied.

312 Precipitated calcite layers were observed on the brick surface and new crystal growths
313 were formed in the pores of the ceramic pieces. In addition, some physical adsorption
314 was also observed.

315 An acceptable carbonation and/or CO₂ capture levels have been achieved under
316 favourable conditions of low pressure and temperature, with low energy costs and
317 therefore environmental protection.

318 These results open the possibility for future studies on using exhausted quarries filled
319 with brick wastes, which could be directly carbonated by injecting CO₂ “in situ”.

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322 AUTHOR INFORMATION

323 Corresponding Author

324 Domingo Martín, dmartin5@us.es, ORCID Id: orcid.org/0000-0003-3725-6598

325 Authors

326 Domingo Martín, dmartin5@us.es, ORCID Id: orcid.org/0000-0003-3725-6598

327 Patricia Aparicio, paparicio@us.es, ORCID Id: orcid.org/0000-0001-5307-1433

328 Emilio Galán, egalan@us.es, ORCID Id: orcid.org/0000-0002-8466-5047

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331 **Present Addresses**

332 Departamento Cristalografía, Mineralogía y Química Agrícola, Facultad de Química,
333 Universidad de Sevilla, Calle Profesor García González, 1, Sevilla 41012, Spain

334 **Author Contributions**

335 The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given
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347

348 **ABBREVIATIONS**

349 APC, air pollution control; BET, Brunauer, Emmett and Teller specific surface; C.E.,
350 carbonation efficiency; CCS, carbon capture and storage; DTA-TG, simultaneous
351 thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis; E.C., experimental capture; EAF,

352 electric arc furnace; GHG, greenhouse gases; ICP-OES, inductively coupled plasma
353 optical emission spectrometry; LOI, loss on ignition performed; SEM, scanning electron
354 microscope; T.C., theoretical capture; XRD, X-ray diffraction; XRF, X-ray fluorescence.

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479

480 **List of tables and figures:**

481 **Table 1.** Experimental parameter values during the carbonation reaction tests.

482 **Table 2.** Major oxide composition (wt%) by XRF of selected bricks.

483 **Table 3.** Mineralogical composition (wt%) of selected bricks.

484 **Table 4.** Granulometric fractions of the crushed samples (wt%).

485 **Table 5.** Carbonation Efficiency (C.E.) according to Stenoir's equation and corrected.

486

487 **Figure 1.** Mineralogical evolution of MPC2 after 720 hours of reaction, with three particle
488 sizes. a) MPC2 with significant detail, b) AUC1 with significant detail, and c) MSC1.

489 **Figure 2.** a) Soluble Ca, Mg, and Si ions measured in untreated and treated MPC2 after
490 240 and 720 hours of reaction; b) Soluble Ca (divided by 10), Mg, and Si ions measured
491 in untreated and treated AUC1 after 240 and 720 hours of reaction; c) Soluble Ca (/10),
492 Mg (/10), and Si ions measured in untreated and treated MSC1 after 240 and 720 hours
493 of reaction.

494 **Figure 3.** Calcite content calculated by C-content (solid line) and DTA-TG (dot-line)
495 analysis as a function of reaction time for (a) MPC2, (b) AUC1 and (c) MSC1.

496 **Figure 4.** Specific surface evolution by BET as a function of reaction time for (a) MPC2,
497 (b) AUC1 and (c) MSC1.

498 **Figure 5.** Vitreous aspect observed by a) stereomicroscope and b) SEM for AUC1 after
499 240 hours of treatment.

500 **Figure 6.** a) Squamous aspect of calcite observed by stereomicroscope and b)
501 aggregates of tabular habit by SEM.

502 **Figure 7.** Crystal growth observed by a) stereomicroscope, b) SEM, and c) 3D optical
503 profiler for MPC2 after 720 hours of treatment.

504 **Figure 8.** a) Aggregates of laminar habit and b) aggregates of dendritic growth.

505 **Figure 9.** Layer of calcite on the surface of MPC2, observed by stereomicroscope after
506 720 hours of treatment.